

ELIMINATION OF DEFECTS IN THE TEACHER'S SPEECH COMMUNICATION WITH CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7445477>

Speech disorders in children can be congenital or acquired. In the first three months of pregnancy, the mother has a severe cold with viral diseases, passing them on the leg without treatment, taking various medications arbitrarily, the father or mother's consumption of drugs, alcohol and tobacco products, as a result of radiation, pelvic narrowness. When the child's brain is crushed, wrapped around the umbilical cord, suffocated, the placenta does not reach the child, the child may have speech defects.

Also, from birth to the age of three, the child suffers from serious infectious diseases, receives various brain injuries, does not speak to the child from the beginning of development, does not say words in full and by his own name, and asks questions when he begins to speak. Failure to respond, not pronouncing sounds correctly can also cause speech defects.

Parents and grandparents like to talk to their child or grandchild in their "child's language". If you call bread "nana", cat "meow", puppy "wow-wow", the child will remember their names in this way. As a result, speech delay is observed in the child.

Apart from these, another aspect that parents should pay attention to is the child's diet. After teething, it is necessary to add chewable foods and fruits and vegetables to porridges and purees, easy-to-swallow foods. In many cases, parents also grate fruits so that the child does not have difficulty biting something hard.

But it's wrong to do this all the time. A child cannot learn to chew. The task of the tooth is to chew and do it after coming out. Chewing helps the teeth and jaws to develop properly, the mobility of the tongue improves, and the child pronounces sounds in accordance with his age.

Children with normal hearing and brain activity start to "agu-gugu" from 1.5-2 months. When his relatives talk to him, the boy replies "agu-gugu". From 5-6 months to 8-11 months, he pronounces easy-to-pronounce lip-lip sounds, lip-tongue sounds.

A healthy child should be able to pronounce ten words easily at the age of one. In general, age is a time when mental, speech and physical development begin in parallel. A lot of talking with the child should not be delayed from this period. For example, if you are traveling together in a car, you should give a little idea about the car, saying, "This is the car, it will take us to our destination." Or, when cutting an apple to a child, it is necessary to tell about its shape, color, taste, where it is brought from, and its benefits. These will settle in the child's memory and gradually increase the wealth of the lexical vocabulary.

One year old - eight months - two years old child can make simple sentences. The reason is that verbs begin to appear in his speech during this period. The number of words a child can use up to the age of two should reach 60-80. After that, he starts saying x, y sounds. At this time, he may not yet say some sounds such as r, sh, j, l, ch, and this is considered the norm.

In general, at the age of two years, speaking is an important part of a child's speech, even before the pronunciation of sounds. That is, there may be defects in the pronunciation of sounds, but he must be able to speak syllables, words, and simple sentences.

It is a worrying situation that he does not speak even at the age of two. In addition to the factors listed above, it can be caused by neurological and auditory diseases. Then it is necessary to take the child to a speech therapist. He checks where there is a problem and directs him to specialists such as audiologist, neuropathologist, psychoneurologist, ENT.

If a child knows and uses 1,000 words between three and four years old, 2,000 words between four and five years old, and about 3,000 words when he is over five years old, his speech development is at a normal level. A five-year-old child has formed the pronunciation of all sounds, and he can retell a story based on a picture.

Three days a week, 45 minutes. Speech therapist training does not interfere with school lessons

It is relatively easier to overcome speech defects in childhood. That is why children with certain speech defects are trained by a specialist in speech therapy centers in kindergartens and schools.

I don't know if there is a speech therapist in every school in Uzbekistan, but it should be in almost all schools in Tashkent.

Speech is a means of expressing thoughts, expressed in oral and written form. Thought occurs with the help of speech, and because of this, people communicate with each other. If oral speech reaches the listener through

pauses, accents, intonation and sounds, written speech is based on a certain regularity of letters and words, punctuation marks, various separations, grammaticalization of sentences.

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